

Dynamic Queue Management for Airport Security Using Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract

Airport security is a primary bottleneck affecting both operational efficiency and passenger experience. Queue management systems can balance load across security lanes by reconfiguring motorised passenger guidance gates, but current deployments typically rely on threshold-based heuristics that require manual per-airport tuning and adapt only weakly to real-time conditions. This study investigates whether a reinforcement learning (RL) agent can outperform such a rule-based baseline for real-time passenger routing. We formulate the control problem as a Markov Decision Process and train a maskable Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) agent on a discrete-event passenger-flow simulation of a complex three-queue airport layout, using a multi-component shaped reward and a four-phase curriculum. The trained policy is evaluated against the operational threshold-based baseline on 24 two-hour windows of replayed historical data covering low-, medium-, and high-traffic conditions, using paired non-parametric tests and bootstrap confidence intervals. The RL agent achieved statistically significant gains in throughput per hour ($\Delta \approx +121$ passengers, $p = 0.006$) and in the exit-entry ratio, the principal stability indicator ($\Delta = +0.03$, $p = 0.0001$), maintaining near-balanced flow under high load where the baseline showed signs of queue accumulation. Mean weighted waiting time was reduced directionally ($\Delta = -0.40$ minutes) but did not reach significance ($p = 0.089$), and waiting-time disparity between entry points was statistically indistinguishable between policies. The agent’s gains were accompanied by a large, statistically robust increase in control activity (approximately +70 route switches per hour). The findings indicate that a learned, real-time routing policy can outperform a hand-crafted threshold-based system under heavy congestion, while highlighting reward-shaping as the key lever for reconciling throughput with operational stability.

1. Introduction

Every departing air passenger must pass through a security screening checkpoint, regardless of destination or travel class. Because the entire departing population converges on a single screening area, the security checkpoint is inherently the primary bottleneck of an airport terminal, and short, smoothly managed waiting times are essential for both operational efficiency and passenger experience.

Modern queue management systems can mitigate this bottleneck by controlling a set of motorised passenger guidance gates (“smart gates”) positioned throughout the waiting area. The system studied in this work is the commercial queue management system developed by Qmetrix GmbH and deployed at major European airports. By changing gate orientations, the system defines the route passengers follow from the queue entrance to the security lanes (“service points”), selecting the most appropriate route in real time according to current demand. When passenger numbers are low, the gates form a short, direct route that minimises walking distance; as demand rises, they reconfigure into longer, winding routes that increase the capacity of the waiting area and prevent queues from spilling into adjacent parts of the terminal. This automated reconfiguration replaces manual repositioning of belt barriers by staff, reducing operational overhead and enabling continuous adaptation to demand.

This operational system currently selects routes using a threshold-based algorithm driven by the number of passengers in each queue. Because of the interdependencies between queues and the unique layout of each airport, this rule-based approach has inherent limitations: it must be manually adapted to each installation, which is time-consuming, and it is unclear whether the full optimisation potential of the system is ever reached.

Reinforcement learning (RL) offers an alternative in which an agent learns a control policy by interacting with an environment and receiving numerical reward, discovering effective strategies through trial and error rather than being programmed with explicit rules [19]. This makes RL

well suited to complex, dynamic problems where the optimal behaviour is difficult to specify in advance.

1.1. Related work

Research on airport operations spans passenger-flow analysis, resource allocation, and scheduling, with several studies focusing specifically on waiting-time optimisation at check-in, security, and boarding [2–5, 8, 21]. A common approach models airport processes using queuing theory or simulation. For example, prior work has proposed mathematical models of security-checkpoint passenger flow with improvements such as dedicated fast lanes [22], and Monte Carlo simulation has been used to determine the optimal number of open lanes from current queue lengths [17, 23]. These studies operate on static or predictive data rather than adapting dynamically to real-time conditions.

A second body of work combines simulation and machine learning to estimate or predict waiting times: closed-circuit television footage has been used to count passengers and train regression models for waiting-time prediction [25], and whole-airport simulations have analysed the effect of passenger profiles on waiting times and resource utilisation [21]. Simulation-based decision-support systems have also been proposed, including comparisons of waiting-time-reduction strategies [3] and optimisation frameworks for staff scheduling and lane allocation using guided simulated annealing and integer linear programming [4]. These frameworks are predominantly offline or pre-scheduled: they estimate configurations from historical patterns and do not actively respond to changing arrivals or queue dynamics in real time.

Real-time dynamic optimisation using RL in this specific context appears to be largely unexplored. Adjacent work demonstrates the promise of the approach: a Deep Q-Network (DQN) has been used to decide minute-by-minute bus dispatching from current demand, capacity, and waiting times [1], and PPO has been applied to stochastic queueing-network control, where the resulting policies consistently outperform state-of-the-art heuristics across light-to-heavy traffic [6]. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, real-time RL-based control has not previously been applied to airport security waiting-queue management. This study addresses that gap.

1.2. Research question and contribution

The central question of this work is: *Can an RL agent outperform a rule-based algorithm for optimising passenger flow and waiting times at airport security checkpoints?*

To answer it, the problem is formalised as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), a PPO agent is trained on a simulation of a complex real-world airport layout, and its performance is compared against the operational threshold-based algorithm using metrics including weighted waiting time,

Figure 1. Overview of the methodology, showing the four main components of the workflow: the passenger simulation (I), the custom Gymnasium environment (II), the PPO training script (III), and the evaluation pipeline (IV).

throughput per hour, exit–entry ratio, and waiting-time disparity between queues. Beyond the immediate question, the work contributes to applied RL by demonstrating the practical viability of learned control policies in large-scale, real-world queue management.

2. Methods

The methodology comprises four components: (I) a passenger simulation provided by Qmetrix GmbH; (II) a custom Gymnasium environment that interfaces the simulation with the RL agent and defines the MDP; (III) a PPO training pipeline using curriculum learning; and (IV) an evaluation pipeline that replays recorded operational data through the simulation to compare the trained agent against the threshold-based baseline under identical conditions. An overview of the workflow is shown in Fig. 1.

2.1. Problem setting and terminology

The control problem is defined over a queueing system in which each *queue* comprises a single entry point and a set of pre-defined *routes* to a subset of *service points* (individual screening lanes, each with a fixed service rate in passengers per hour). At any time, exactly one route is active per queue; changing the active route is a *switch*, constrained by a hard minimum 30-second switch lock that prevents disruptive rapid changes. Where two adjacent queues share service points, a *balancer* (a virtual dividing line) partitions the shared points between them and can be shifted in favour of the higher-demand queue.

The evaluated airport was selected for the complexity of its layout, which exercises all three major control aspects of the problem simultaneously: *long–short* route selection (matching route length to queue occupancy), *routing* (directing passengers toward less congested service points),

and *balancing* (partitioning shared service points between adjacent queues). The system has three queues—West, East, and Temp. West and East share most of their service points (service rate 400 passengers per hour) and require both routing and balancing decisions; Temp is a purely long–short queue (service rate 180 passengers per hour) that acts as an overflow extension of East, with the East and Temp entrances being mutually exclusive. Because this represents one of the most complex layouts in which Qmetrix GmbH’s system is deployed, successful control provides strong evidence of applicability to simpler layouts.

Key evaluation quantities are defined as follows. The waiting time of a queue is estimated from its occupancy and exit rate via Little’s Law [12], $WT_{q,t} = n_{q,t}/\lambda_{q,t}$, where $n_{q,t}$ is the number of passengers in queue q at time t and $\lambda_{q,t}$ is the exit rate determined by the number of open service points and their service rates. When aggregating across queues, the weighted waiting time (WWT) is the passenger-count-weighted average of per-queue waiting times. Waiting-time disparity (WTD) is the absolute difference between the West waiting time and the passenger-weighted East/Temp waiting time, capturing fairness across entry points. Throughput is the realised processing rate (exits per hour), and the exit–entry ratio (EER) is the ratio of total exits to total entries over a window: a value near 1.0 indicates stable flow, below 1.0 indicates queue accumulation, and above 1.0 indicates backlog clearance.

2.2. Passenger simulation

The simulation is a discrete-time model that updates passenger positions at one-second intervals. Passengers enter a queue and follow the active route to the service points, where they are processed at the queue’s exit rate. Each simulated passenger is assigned a unique identifier and randomly drawn characteristics (gender, travel purpose, step distance, and relationship to the person ahead) that determine spacing and produce realistic crowd dynamics without explicit crowd simulation. The model represents economy-class passengers only; higher classes and passengers with reduced mobility use dedicated lanes outside the scope of the controlled system.

To expose the agent to a wide range of conditions, three parameters are randomised across training episodes:

- **Entry rate.** Modelled as overlapping Gaussian peaks reproducing characteristic morning, midday, and evening demand on a base rate, with elevated rates for weekends and holidays. A starting hour and day type (weekday/weekend/holiday) are drawn at episode start (probabilities 0.5, 0.3, 0.2), and second-by-second arrivals are sampled from a Poisson process [16] matching the rate curve.
- **Exit rate.** The full set of service-point configurations

is reduced to four representative subsets (*All*, *Very Busy*, *Medium Busy*, *Not Busy*); one is selected at random per episode.

- **Initial queue occupancy.** Drawn randomly up to a maximum of 25 passengers per queue to avoid initialising in an unrecoverable overflow state.

Episodes are seeded for reproducibility. Episode length ranges from 600 steps (10 minutes) to 7 200 steps (2 hours) and increases over training as part of the curriculum schedule.

2.3. MDP formulation

A custom Gymnasium environment [20] wraps the simulation, provides a standardised interface compatible with Stable-Baselines3 (SB3) [15], and handles invalid-action masking.

Observation space. The observation space is designed so that every variable is available in the real operational system, ensuring a trained policy could in principle be deployed without additional instrumentation. It comprises global observations (per-service-point open/closed status; current balancer position) and per-queue observations (selected route; route utilisation; waiting time; exit rate; total passengers; passengers entered/exited; and per-zone passenger counts). Additional variables support reward computation (previous action, previous balancer position, previous walking times, previous waiting-time disparity, and previous passenger-count disparity across open service points). The switch-lock state is exposed directly through four observations—a switch-permitted indicator, time elapsed since the last switch, time remaining until the lock lifts, and the current lock duration ($T_{\text{lock}} \in [30, 60]$ s)—so the agent can plan around the constraint rather than learning it implicitly through penalties.

Action space. The agent controls the active route for each queue. Rather than selecting routes independently, the action space is defined as the set of all *valid* combinations of route choices across the three queues, represented as tuples (West, East, Temp). West and East each have five routes; Temp has three; East and Temp additionally include a CLOSED route reflecting their mutual exclusivity. This combination-based formulation is much smaller than the Cartesian product of individual choices and allows physically invalid combinations (e.g. East and Temp both open, or collision-inducing West/East pairs) to be excluded at construction time. The agent samples from a probability distribution over valid actions, balancing exploitation and exploration; exploration is encouraged through a PPO entropy bonus weighted by an entropy coefficient.

Invalid-action masking. Beyond statically excluded combinations, some actions become invalid dynamically (e.g. a route whose service points are all closed, or a balancer shift requiring the vacated routes to be empty first). A binary mask $m_t \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{A}|}$ is constructed each timestep; invalid actions are assigned zero probability before sampling [11]. This accelerates learning and prevents misleading reward signals from actions that should never have been available.

Reward function. As there is no natural terminal state, the agent receives an intermediate reward at every timestep, computed as a weighted sum of one positive component and several penalties:

$$r_{\text{total}} = r_{\text{throughput}} - p_{\text{overflow}} \pm p_{\text{walk}} \pm p_{\text{disparity}} \pm p_{\text{pax}} - p_{\text{switch}} - p_{\text{balancer}} \quad (1)$$

The dominant positive signal is a throughput reward ($r_{\text{throughput}}$) proportional to the number of passengers exiting per timestep. A two-tier capacity-overflow penalty (p_{overflow}) is applied when any route exceeds 90% or 100% of capacity; its large magnitude makes overflow avoidance effectively a hard constraint. The walking-time (p_{walk}) and waiting-time-disparity ($p_{\text{disparity}}$) penalties are applied to the *change* relative to the previous timestep (rewarding improvements and penalising degradations symmetrically). A passenger-disparity penalty (p_{pax}) discourages increases in the standard deviation of passengers per open service point, encouraging even utilisation. A tiered switching penalty (p_{switch})—with exponential decay within a minimum interval, a flat penalty within a comfort zone, and a reduced penalty thereafter—discourages unnecessarily frequent switches, with an additional penalty proportional to the magnitude of any accompanying balancer move (p_{balancer}). The final reward weights (Tab. 1) were determined through iterative manual experimentation until stable, improving training curves were obtained across all curriculum phases.

In the present implementation the agent does not control the balancer explicitly; the balancer is shifted implicitly as a consequence of route selection (moved only as far as necessary to accommodate a selected route), with the balancer-move penalty applied proportionally. Explicit balancer control is identified as future work.

2.4. Algorithm and training

The RL problem is on-policy in preference (stability and scalability to a large discrete action space outweigh sample efficiency here), discrete (routes are pre-defined configurations), and best addressed with a stochastic policy (for exploration during training). Proximal Policy Optimisation

Table 1. Reward component weights used in the final training run.

Component	Weight
Throughput reward ($p_{\text{throughput}}$)	15.00
Capacity overflow penalty (p_{overflow})	100.00
Walking-time penalty (p_{walk})	0.01
Waiting-time disparity penalty (p_{disp})	0.30
Passenger disparity penalty (p_{pax})	0.50
Switching penalty (p_{switch})	0.50
Balancer-move penalty (p_{balancer})	0.05

(PPO) satisfies all three requirements [18]. PPO optimises a clipped surrogate objective that limits the size of each policy update, improving stability over vanilla policy-gradient methods, and uses an actor-critic architecture. Because the standard SB3 PPO does not support action masking, the MaskablePPO implementation from stable-baselines3-contrib [11] was used; it extends the Stable-Baselines3 PPO [15] with invalid-action masking, setting the logits of masked actions to $-\infty$ before the softmax. The default network configuration was retained: the flattened observation vector feeds separate fully connected policy (actor) and value (critic) networks, each with two hidden layers of 64 units and Tanh activations. The actor outputs logits over the $|\mathcal{A}|$ valid action combinations and the critic a scalar state-value estimate.

Curriculum learning. To prevent the agent from being overwhelmed by the full task before learning basic routing, training proceeds through four phases of increasing complexity [14], summarised in Tab. 2. New penalty terms, service-point configurations, and environmental conditions are introduced progressively. Phase transitions occur at fixed step counts (200k, 600k, and 1M steps); to avoid abrupt mid-episode changes, new phase parameters take effect only at the start of the next episode.

Training setup. Each run consisted of 2×10^6 steps (one step = one second of simulated time) and was trained on a single NVIDIA RTX 4000 GPU (20 GB VRAM) hosted on a cloud virtual machine, taking approximately 1.5 hours per run. Hyperparameters were tuned using Bayesian optimisation and experiment tracking across five runs, selecting the configuration with the highest mean episodic reward. The selected configuration used MaskablePPO with learning rate 3.0×10^{-4} , entropy coefficient 7.0×10^{-4} , batch size 2048, discount factor $\gamma = 0.995$, and GAE $\lambda = 0.98$; other hyperparameters retained SB3 defaults. With only five tuning runs, this represents the best configuration found within a limited search rather than a global optimum, and a more extensive search could yield further gains. The mean episodic reward over training followed the expected

Table 2. Curriculum phases. Each phase progressively introduces additional penalty terms and environmental conditions.

Phase	Focus	Service points / entry rate	Episode length	New elements
1 (0–200k)	Basic routing; balance waiting times	All, Very Busy; weekdays	30–60 min	Walking, overflow, WTD penalties; Temp disabled
2 (200k–600k)	Even passenger distribution	All, Very Busy; weekdays	30–60 min	+ Passenger disparity penalty
3 (600k–1M)	Complex scenarios; limit switching	All subsets; weekdays, weekends, holidays	60–120 min	+ Switching & balancer-move penalties
4 (1M+)	Full scenario range	All subsets; weekdays, weekends, holidays	20–120 min	+ Temp queue enabled

curriculum-driven pattern, with recovery and continued improvement after each phase transition, indicating successful adaptation to each new set of constraints.

2.5. Evaluation

The trained agent and the threshold-based baseline were compared under identical conditions by replaying recorded operational data through the same simulation and Gymnasium environment used in training. The recorded data consisted of one-second snapshots from the live system (service-point status; per-queue and per-zone passenger counts; per-queue entries; and the baseline’s routing decisions), stored in a time-series database, drawn from a two-week period in November 2025 covering weekdays and weekends. No public holidays were available within the recording period, which is a limitation given the elevated and less predictable demand characteristic of holidays.

For each window, the simulation was initialised with the recorded passenger counts, route selections, and balancer position at the window start; at each subsequent timestep it was fed the recorded service-point statuses and per-queue entry counts. Each window was run twice under identical conditions—once with the RL agent making routing decisions, and once replaying the recorded baseline actions—enabling a direct, paired comparison.

Buffer mechanism and confound. Because the simulation’s maximum simultaneous passenger capacity is lower than the real-system peak, a buffer was added at each queue entrance: when an entry is recorded but the corresponding queue is at capacity, the passenger is held and admitted as soon as space becomes available. This enables replay despite the capacity constraint but introduces a confound: if one policy manages occupancy more effectively, it admits buffered passengers sooner, processing a different number of passengers over the same window. This asymmetry tends to *underestimate* the RL agent’s waiting-time

advantage and to *inflate* its measured throughput advantage, and is accounted for in interpretation.

Windows and metrics. Evaluation used 24 two-hour windows (7 200 timesteps each), selected to span morning, midday, evening, shoulder, and night slots across week-day and weekend patterns and three traffic levels—low (0–99 passengers), medium (100–249), and high (250–400)—classified by the highest single-queue occupancy in the window. The first 15 minutes of each window were excluded to remove start-up transients. The reported metrics are mean and 95th-percentile weighted waiting time (\overline{WWT} , WWT_{95}), throughput per hour (TPH), exit–entry ratio (EER), mean and 95th-percentile waiting-time disparity (\overline{WTD} , WTD_{95}), switches per hour (SPH), and balancer moves per hour (BPH).

Statistical tests. Significance was assessed on paired per-window deltas (RL – baseline) across the 24 windows using two complementary methods: the Wilcoxon signed-rank test [7, 24], a non-parametric paired test of whether the median delta differs from zero (with $p < 0.05$ taken as evidence of a consistent, systematic difference); and a 95% bootstrap confidence interval (CI) for the mean paired delta [9], estimated by resampling the 24 deltas with replacement. An interval lying entirely on the favourable side of zero provides additional evidence of a robust directional advantage; an interval crossing zero leaves the sign of the advantage uncertain. No correction for multiple comparisons was applied across the eight reported metrics; the two strongest results (EER and SPH) remain significant under any standard family-wise or false-discovery-rate correction, and the non-significant waiting-time results are unaffected, so a correction would not alter the study’s conclusions.

3. Results

All metrics are reported as paired RL – baseline deltas across the 24 evaluation windows. Summary statistics are given in Tab. 3.

3.1. Weighted waiting time

The RL agent produced a clear distributional shift toward lower mean weighted waiting time, with a median of approximately 4.0 minutes versus approximately 5.5 minutes for the baseline (a reduction of roughly 27%), and a more compact distribution concentrated below 7 minutes (Fig. 2). The separation was most pronounced in high- and medium-traffic windows; low-traffic windows clustered near optimal for both policies. Nonetheless, the aggregate statistics fell short of conventional significance: the mean delta of -0.40 minutes had a bootstrap CI of $[-1.05, 0.29]$ that crosses zero, and the Wilcoxon test gave $p = 0.089$. The apparent tension between the 27% gap in per-policy median waiting times and this small, non-significant paired delta arises because the two quantities are not equivalent: the former compares the median of each policy’s window distribution (unpaired), whereas the significance test operates on the within-window RL – baseline differences, which are dominated by the many low-traffic windows in which both policies perform near-optimally. The 95th-percentile metric was weaker still ($p = 0.26$, $\Delta = -0.09$ minutes), consistent with the higher inherent volatility of tail metrics in a stochastic simulation. The advantage is also evident across the window sample: roughly 65% of RL windows achieved a mean wait below 4.5 minutes, compared with approximately 40% of baseline windows.

Two factors plausibly suppress the measured waiting-time signal. First, the aggregate sample includes many low-traffic windows in which both policies operate near optimum, diluting overall significance; a traffic-level-stratified analysis would be required to quantify the agent’s advantage under congestion more precisely. Second, the buffer mechanism partially penalises the RL agent for its own throughput efficiency by requiring it to serve more passengers, so the true waiting-time benefit may be larger than the measured -0.40 minutes suggests.

3.2. Throughput and exit–entry ratio

The strongest results concerned system capacity and stability (Fig. 3). The RL agent’s TPH distribution was shifted upward and notably more compact (median near 1 000 passengers per hour versus approximately 850 for the baseline, $\approx 18\%$ higher), indicating more consistent performance across traffic conditions. The mean delta of $+120.9$ passengers per hour ($\approx 14\%$ over the baseline median) was supported by a Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.006$) and a bootstrap CI entirely above zero ($[58.5, 186.1]$), confirming a robust, consistent improvement rather than one driven by outliers.

Figure 2. Violin plots of mean weighted waiting time (\overline{WWT} , top) and 95th-percentile weighted waiting time (WWT_{95} , bottom) for the RL agent and the baseline across the 24 evaluation windows. The x -axis distinguishes the two policies and the y -axis shows the metric value in minutes; lower is better. The width of each violin is proportional to the density of windows at that value, a horizontal line marks the median and a vertical line marks the interquartile range. Individual windows are overlaid as points, colour-coded by traffic level (teal: high; orange: medium; purple: low).

The EER produced the strongest statistical result of the entire evaluation ($p = 0.0001$, $\Delta = +0.03$, CI $[0.02, 0.05]$). The RL agent’s distribution was tightly concentrated between 0.95 and 1.05, indicating consistent operation near flow equilibrium, whereas the baseline’s distribution spanned a much wider range (down to approximately 0.66), with a long lower tail corresponding to windows of marked queue accumulation and incipient instability. Although several high-traffic baseline windows fell below 0.90, this pattern was largely absent from the RL results, suggesting the baseline struggles to maintain flow balance even under high demand. Across the window sample, approximately 40% of baseline windows fell below an EER of 0.90, compared with fewer than 20% of RL windows. While the absolute improvement is modest, it carries high practical significance because ratios below 1.0 compound over time into growing backlogs.

As with waiting time, the buffer mechanism affects interpretation: part of the TPH delta may reflect a higher admission rate rather than purely more efficient processing. The EER is less affected, since it relates entries to exits within the same window, making it a more reliable indicator of the agent’s flow-management advantage.

3.3. Waiting-time disparity

On waiting-time disparity, neither policy held a consistent advantage (Fig. 4). The RL agent’s median \overline{WTD} (≈ 4

Table 3. Significance values for all evaluation metrics. The Direction column states the favourable direction for each metric (whether lower or higher is better). Delta is the mean RL – baseline paired difference; CI_{95} is the 95% bootstrap CI of that difference; Wilcoxon p is the p -value of the paired signed-rank test.

Metric	Direction	Delta	CI_{95} Low	CI_{95} High	Wilcoxon p
\overline{WWT}	lower	-0.40	-1.05	0.29	0.089
WWT_{95}	lower	-0.09	-1.40	1.21	0.26
TPH	higher	120.92	58.51	186.12	0.006
EER	higher	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.0001
\overline{WTD}	lower	-0.31	-1.33	0.75	0.29
WTD_{95}	lower	0.30	-1.70	2.32	0.70
SPH	lower	69.52	65.70	72.40	1.82×10^{-5}
BPH	lower	5.77	2.63	8.67	7.42×10^{-4}

Figure 3. Violin plots of throughput per hour (TPH, top) and the exit-entry ratio (EER, bottom) for the RL agent and the baseline across the 24 evaluation windows. The x -axis distinguishes the two policies and the y -axis shows the metric value; for TPH a higher value is better, and for EER values closer to and above 1.0 indicate a balanced flow state. The width of each violin is proportional to the density of windows at that value, a horizontal line marks the median and a vertical line marks the interquartile range. Individual windows are overlaid as points, colour-coded by traffic level (teal: high; orange: medium; purple: low).

minutes) was lower than the baseline’s (≈ 5.5 minutes), but the distributions overlapped substantially: the mean delta of -0.31 minutes had a wide bootstrap CI ($[-1.33, 0.75]$) spanning zero, and the Wilcoxon test gave $p = 0.29$. The tail metric was the weakest result of the evaluation ($\Delta = +0.30$ minutes, $p = 0.70$, CI $[-1.70, 2.32]$), with several high-traffic RL windows producing the largest outliers. This outcome is consistent with a reward function prioritising global throughput and stability over parity between entry points: the agent routes opportunistically to maximise flow, making it neither systematically fairer nor systematically less fair than the baseline. Should equitable service become a higher operational priority, the waiting-

Figure 4. Violin plots of mean waiting-time disparity (\overline{WTD} , top) and 95th-percentile waiting-time disparity (WTD_{95} , bottom) between the two system entry points for the RL agent and the baseline across the 24 evaluation windows. The x -axis distinguishes the two policies and the y -axis shows the absolute waiting-time difference in minutes; lower is better, as it reflects more equitable service across entry points. The width of each violin is proportional to the density of windows at that value, a horizontal line marks the median and a vertical line marks the interquartile range. Individual windows are overlaid as points, colour-coded by traffic level (teal: high; orange: medium; purple: low).

time-disparity penalty weight would need to be increased relative to the throughput reward.

3.4. Switching frequency

The throughput and stability gains were accompanied by a substantial increase in control activity (Fig. 5). The RL agent’s switching frequency was concentrated in a narrow band near 70–75 switches per hour, essentially constant across traffic levels, whereas the baseline’s mass lay below 10 switches per hour. The two distributions were entirely non-overlapping, yielding one of the most statistically robust results in the evaluation (mean delta $+69.5$ switches

Figure 5. Violin plots of switches per hour (SPH, top) and balancer moves per hour (BPH, bottom) for the RL agent and the baseline across the 24 evaluation windows. The x -axis distinguishes the two policies and the y -axis shows the metric value; lower is better for both. The width of each violin is proportional to the density of windows at that value, a horizontal line marks the median and a vertical line marks the interquartile range. Individual windows are overlaid as points, colour-coded by traffic level (teal: high; orange: medium; purple: low).

per hour, $p = 1.82 \times 10^{-5}$, CI [65.7, 72.4])—an increase of more than 700% over the baseline. As lower is better for this metric, this constitutes a clear and consistent regression. The minimum 30-second switch lock imposes a theoretical maximum of 120 switches per hour; the agent’s rate, while below this ceiling, greatly exceeds any apparent operational necessity, given that the baseline achieves comparable disparity results with fewer than 10 switches per hour.

Balancer moves showed a smaller but still significant gap (mean delta +5.77 moves per hour, $\approx 192\%$ over the baseline median, $p = 7.42 \times 10^{-4}$, CI [2.63, 8.67]). Together these results indicate a fundamentally more dynamic and interventionist control strategy.

The operational implications are non-trivial: frequent route changes can disorient passengers already in the queue, split groups travelling together, and reduce compliance with routing instructions—effects not captured by the throughput and waiting-time metrics. The throughput benefit must therefore be weighed against the value of a calmer, more predictable system state. Increasing the switching penalty weight is a well-motivated avenue for encouraging more stable, longer-horizon strategies while ideally preserving most of the throughput gains.

4. Discussion

This section interprets the evaluation results in light of the study’s central question, comparing them with prior work and weighing their operational implications and limi-

tations.

4.1. Main findings

The results are mixed but informative. On the metrics most directly characterising system capacity and stability, the RL agent demonstrated clear and statistically robust superiority: throughput per hour increased by a mean of approximately 121 passengers ($p = 0.006$), and the exit-entry ratio improved significantly ($p = 0.0001$), with the agent sustaining near-balanced flow even under high load where the baseline began to accumulate queues. These results indicate that the agent has learned a policy that coordinates passenger entries more effectively than the hand-crafted threshold logic, particularly near capacity.

On service quality, the picture is less clear. The agent produced a directional reduction in mean weighted waiting time ($\Delta = -0.40$ minutes, $p = 0.089$) that the 24-window sample was insufficiently powered to confirm, and the 95th-percentile waiting time showed no significant difference ($p = 0.26$). These results are consistent with the hypothesis that the agent’s advantage is concentrated in high-traffic conditions and diluted by low-traffic windows; they should be interpreted as inconclusive rather than as evidence of no effect. The agent neither outperformed nor underperformed the baseline on waiting-time disparity ($p = 0.29$ and $p = 0.70$), consistent with a reward function that does not prioritise equitable service.

The clearest regression lies in control activity: the agent performed on average 69.5 additional switches per hour ($p < 0.0001$) and 5.8 additional balancer moves per hour ($p = 0.0007$). This high-frequency intervention is the mechanism through which the agent achieves its throughput advantage, but could cause passenger disruption in a real deployment. Overall, whether the trade-off constitutes a net improvement for a given operator depends on the relative weight placed on peak-load throughput versus predictability and operational simplicity. The behaviour is consistent with a reward function aligned with throughput maximisation that did not penalise disparity and control activity strongly enough; further reward shaping—in particular increasing the switching penalty and refining the curriculum—is likely to improve the balance, given that the agent tended to exploit the least-penalised degree of freedom rather than discovering a globally optimal strategy.

4.2. Comparison with previous work

The findings relate to three strands of prior work. Relative to classical and simulation-based approaches that rely on offline, predictive frameworks [4, 22, 23], the RL agent’s significant TPH and EER gains over a reactive threshold baseline demonstrate that a learned, real-time policy can extract additional performance beyond a well-designed heuristic—consistent with the general finding that adap-

tive policies outperform static configurations under unpredictable demand [3]. Relative to machine-learning prediction approaches that estimate waiting times but leave intervention to human operators [21, 25], the present framework closes the loop between observation and action, directly issuing routing and balancing decisions; the maintenance of a stable EER under high demand illustrates the added value of an autonomous, closed-loop controller.

Relative to RL approaches in adjacent domains, the results are broadly consistent with dynamic bus-dispatching via DQN [1] and with PPO-based queueing-network control, whose heavy-traffic advantages over heuristics [6] mirror the high-demand gains observed here. One notable divergence is that the present agent converges on a near-maximum actuation rate, constrained only by the switch lock; this is attributable to the low switching cost in the reward function—a reward-design issue rather than an intrinsic property of PPO, since the comparable queueing-network study does not report it. This reinforces the conclusion that increasing the switching penalty is a well-motivated next step.

4.3. Implications

The significant throughput and stability improvements suggest that a learned routing policy could reduce the frequency and severity of queue-overflow events at peak times—one of the most operationally disruptive and passenger-visible failure modes of airport terminals. Because the simulation was calibrated against real operational data from the target airport, these findings carry higher practical relevance than results from abstract models. The most directly quantifiable benefit is the reduced risk of unbounded queue growth under high demand, translating in practice into fewer ground-staff interventions and a more predictable flow.

A key organisational advantage is reduced manual configuration. The threshold-based system must be manually tuned per installation, a time-consuming and expertise-dependent process; the RL agent instead learns its policy through interaction with the simulation and can be deployed to a new configuration by retraining on an updated model. Because training occurs entirely in simulation, the policy can be specified before the physical system is operational, decoupling training from operation, reducing commissioning time, and allowing validation across a wide range of simulated scenarios—including rare high-load events—without disrupting live operations.

The principal threat is the high switching frequency, which may produce a passenger experience perceived as chaotic and is most likely addressable through reward shaping. More broadly, deploying an automated decision-making system in a security-critical environment raises accountability and transparency concerns: the opacity of a

learned policy makes it difficult to audit or explain decisions to regulators or passengers, and airports under strict regulatory frameworks may face barriers to adoption without additional interpretability guarantees.

4.4. Limitations

The simulation, while calibrated against operational data, is subject to a known capacity constraint: its maximum simultaneous occupancy falls short of the real-system peak, so the most extreme high-load scenarios—precisely those in which the agent’s stability advantage is hypothesised to be greatest—were not evaluated. The buffer mechanism that partially compensates for this introduces the asymmetric-passenger-count confound discussed above, which conservatively biases the waiting-time results and inflates the absolute TPH delta. A further asymmetry is that the baseline’s actions were recorded on the live system at its full capacity but were replayed through the capacity-reduced simulation, so the baseline operated on decisions that were not tuned for the simulated capacity; this may disadvantage it in ways not fully captured by the buffer analysis. The simulation also does not model equipment faults (e.g. gate or service-point failures), passenger non-compliance with routing instructions, or the physical propagation delay between a gate change and its effect on crowd movement; it further excludes passengers using dedicated lanes (higher classes, reduced mobility, special needs).

The evaluation used 24 windows, sufficient to detect large effects (switching, EER) but underpowered for smaller waiting-time differences; the non-significant waiting-time results should be read as inconclusive rather than null. The reward function characterises one point in the design space rather than the full capability of the approach, and the curriculum design (introduction order, transition step counts, episode lengths) is an additional degree of freedom that could meaningfully change the resulting policy. Finally, the agent was evaluated on the same layout and demand distribution used in training; its ability to generalise to different configurations or demand patterns has not been tested, and the high-frequency reactive policy may be closely tuned to the specific simulated dynamics.

4.5. Future work

The most immediate priority is reward-function refinement, in particular increasing the switching penalty and waiting-time-disparity term, ideally via a systematic reward-component analysis (e.g. holding one metric at a target level while varying others) and a grid or Bayesian search over the weight space to map achievable trade-offs between throughput, disparity, and switching frequency. The curriculum introduces an additional layer of interdependency, and systematic variation of phase transitions and penalty-introduction order would reveal the policy’s sensitivity to

curriculum design. Evaluating alternative algorithms (e.g. a discrete-action Soft Actor-Critic [10] or DQN with masking [1], or a multi-agent formulation [13] controlling individual queues) would strengthen the generalisability of the conclusions. A traffic-level-stratified evaluation would more precisely characterise when and why the agent outperforms the baseline. Closing the simulation capacity gap would enable training and evaluation under the most demanding conditions. Generalisation should be tested at two levels: near-transfer (minor layout variations without retraining, including simulated equipment failure) and far-transfer (a new agent trained from scratch on a substantially different terminal). Exposing the balancer as an explicit control variable could enable finer-grained capacity allocation. Ultimately, a controlled live pilot study would reveal passenger compliance rates and the operational acceptability of the agent’s switching frequency, validating the simulation-based findings or exposing simulation-to-reality gaps.

4.6. Conclusion

This study investigated whether a reinforcement learning agent can outperform a threshold-based algorithm for managing passenger flow through an airport security waiting-queue system. A PPO-based agent, trained entirely in simulation, achieved statistically significant improvements in throughput and queue stability over the existing rule-based system—particularly under high-load conditions—without requiring manual per-airport configuration: throughput per hour increased by a mean of 121 passengers ($p = 0.006$) and the exit–entry ratio improved by 0.03 ($p = 0.0001$). Waiting-time reductions remained directional but inconclusive ($\Delta = -0.40$ minutes, $p = 0.089$), and control activity was substantially higher (approximately 70 additional route switches per hour, $\approx 700\%$ above the baseline). These findings establish reinforcement learning as a viable and promising alternative to hand-crafted heuristics for real-time queue management in airport operations, with clear directions for refinement through reward shaping and curriculum adjustment.

Author Contributions

Anna Marie Punzengruber conducted the research as part of the master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master’s thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Rosana de Oliveira Gomes supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare the following competing interests: this research was conducted during the first author’s employment at Qmetrix GmbH, whose threshold-based queue management system serves as the baseline for comparison, and whose simulation environment was used for training and evaluation. Every effort was made to ensure the objectivity of the evaluation, including the use of pre-defined metrics, statistical testing, and a simulation environment reflecting the operational system as closely as possible.

Data Availability

The source code for the custom Gymnasium environment, training pipeline, evaluation scripts, and analysis code, together with the evaluation data, are proprietary to Qmetrix GmbH and are not publicly available due to commercial confidentiality.

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